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“AWAKE, YOU WHO SLUMBERS!”

Awake, you who slumbers!
In the morning mist!
Tarry, not a moment
Arise, revere Him!

Awake, you who slumbers!
With the sonorous echo,
Exalt, He who is eternal.
Praise, He who is faithful.

Awake, you who slumbers!
In righteousness, fear Him.
Cast off works of iniquity.
Draw nigh to Elohim!

Awake, you who slumbers!
For the day of reckoning is forthcoming.
Rise from your bed, my friend.
And, start praying!